

International Conference

Public Communication and Artificial Intelligence

Impact and Consequences

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University of Bucharest, Faculty of Journalism and Communication Sciences
Institut de la Communication and Laboratoire Education, Cultures, Politiques
de l'Université Lumière Lyon 2, France

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Public Communication and Artificial Intelligence: Impact and consequences

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Artificial Intelligence - a ubiquitous subject in the media, and everyday discussions - has quickly become a central theme in calls for projects and scientific events of many research centres and in various organisations. However, the real impact of AI on various sectors such as education, media production, decision-making etc., has yet to be explored.

The goal of the conference is to provide a view on the state of research in communication in the context of recent technological innovations. It adopts a critical and comparative perspective, examining both perceptions and practices associated with AI in the academic environment, particularly in the field of communication and media training. We seek contributions that analyze the construction of the AI concept in the public sphere by examining recent discourses, and by studying the perceptions of students and teachers on the use of AI, as well as to map academic practices that integrate these technologies. The conference focuses on the challenges to which journalism, public communication, and education are exposed in the context of the increased diversification of digital technologies.

ORGANISERS

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A

Liliana ABREU (Universidade Nova de Lisboa) & Alexandre DUARTE (Universidade Nova de Lisboa): *Femvertising or Femwashing? The impact of authenticity on consumer purchase intention*

This article seeks to analyze the impact of authenticity in femvertising campaigns consumers' purchase intention. Femvertising has been considered as a winning marketing strategy because it can improve consumer attitudes, reduce ad resistance and increase purchase intentions. However, the Femvertising campaigns are not perceived by all consumers as sincere (femwashing). Consumers can detect the authenticity of an ad and therefore thus, qualified to identify ambivalences between the brand and the advertising message. An incongruence between the message and the brand can lead to distrust and skepticism of the public in relation to the brand and its motives, so it is possible that the campaign advertising does not achieve the expected objectives. Thus, authenticity is a prerequisite for an effective and successful femvertising ad and, only if authenticity is verified, namely through the alignment of the brand's objective and explicit values with your marketing messages, femvertising will impact purchase intent.

Laura AMIGO (Università della Svizzera Italiana, Institute of Media and Journalism) & Colin PORLEZZA (Università della Svizzera Italiana, Institute of Media and Journalism): *How Are Swiss News Organizations Ensuring a Responsible Approach to AI Technology?*

The increasing integration of AI in news work (Cools, 2022; de-Lima-Santos & Ceron, 2021), poses new ethical challenges (Porlezza & Ferri, 2022) that news media address mainly through self-regulatory means such as guidelines or codes of ethics (Becker et al., 2023). The responsible use of AI in journalism entails therefore the identification and enactment of central values in relation to the design, implementation and use of this technology to constantly evaluate and "improve the way journalistic AI lives up to these values" (Helberger et al., 2022, p. 1620).

Drawing on a governance (Dafoe, 2018) and media accountability approach (Eberwein, Fengler and Karmasin, 2019), this contribution wants to shed light on how Swiss news organizations approach AI- systems responsibly by looking at:

RQ1) How and to what extent is AI technology regulated in organizational codes of ethics or guidelines?

RQ2) How do journalists perceive AI integration in newsrooms?

Empirically, the research is based on a two-step methodology: First, we collected 30 ethical codes and guidelines published by the most relevant Swiss news media as part of an ongoing Horizon Europe project called "Diacomet". Secondly, we carried out a focus group with 5 participants and 11 semi-structured interviews between October 2023 and June 2024 with journalists working in Swiss newsrooms.

We asked them to describe their perceptions, particularly regarding opportunities and (ethical) risks. We then applied an inductive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2012) of the selected documents and the collected discursive material to identify key themes on how a responsible use of AI-systems is understood, regulated, and accounted for. The paper sheds light on AI governance approaches aimed at strengthening responsible public communication in times of disruptive technological changes that affect both journalism and democracy.

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Antonio AMUZA (Universitatea din București). *The use of artificial intelligence in political communication: The impact of ChatGPT on young voters in the context of the construction of social authenticity*

In the context of increasingly low trust in the political class, this research aims to investigate how the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in political communication can influence the perceptions and electoral behaviors of young people aged 18 to 35.

The primary objective of this research is to identify a series of archetypes in the audience of political messages, defined by how citizens relate to the predom-

inantly communicated themes. Secondly, we aim to understand if and how AI, through language models such as ChatGPT, can contribute to reducing the trust gap between young people and the political class. Given the predominantly negative perception of politics among young people, we are studying whether AI can be an effective tool in revitalizing political communication and creating messages that resonate more deeply with this segment of the electorate. By analyzing the identified voter clusters, we aim to highlight the characteristics of each and explore how advanced technologies can be used to improve political engagement and, implicitly, trust in the democratic system.

The study, conducted on a national sample of over 800 young people, identified four distinct categories of voters based on 26 analytical variables. These variables were formulated as statements to which respondents were asked to position themselves, providing a detailed picture of their opinions and trust levels in political and social institutions. One of the identified clusters shows a greater inclination towards trust in international organizations such as the EU and NATO, as well as NGOs. Citizens in this group believe that Romania is not sufficiently oriented towards young people or citizens in general, although they show significant intention to participate in voting, including parliamentary and presidential elections (Z-score: 0.44740, 0.48702, 0.43436).

According to theories of social authenticity, such as those developed by Phillip Vannini, authenticity is essential for building trust in social relationships. Vannini emphasizes that authenticity is perceived through the congruence between the actions and values expressed by individuals and organizations (Vannini, 2006). In the context of political campaigns, the authenticity of the messages conveyed is crucial for gaining and maintaining the electorate's trust. However, AI-generated content raises questions about authenticity, as AI can create messages perceived as artificial and lacking genuineness. Recent studies indicate that the use of pre-defined messages, such as those generated by ChatGPT, in political campaigns can have ambivalent effects.

In conclusion, while AI has the potential to transform political campaigns and improve communication with voters, it must be used judiciously to avoid perceptions of inauthenticity and social disconnection.

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Mónika ANDOK (Pázmány Péter Catholic University), András RADEZKY (Pázmány Péter Catholic University), Dóra P. SZILCZL (Pázmány Péter Catholic University) & Zoltán RAJKI (Pázmány Péter Catholic University): *The use of artificial intelligence by Hungarian journalists and their attitudes related to AI*

The presentation revolves around how the advent of artificial intelligence has affected the journalism profession, including religious content producers. First, it presents when the changes related to online technology appeared in the history of journalism, and then it goes around the areas where artificial intelligence applications can be adapted in the work processes of content generation, distribution, and moderation. After that, the study describes a two-stage empirical research, the first step of which was a qualitative survey of journalists in the fall of 2023, using an in-depth interview methodology. In the framework of this qualitative research, we approached 40 Hungarian journalists and content producers and conducted in-depth interviews with them. In the case of the in-depth interviews, we looked for gender differences, as well as differences that stem from the institutional system of journalism. After that, the presentation of the results of the quantitative research that took place in the spring of 2024 will follow. We conducted a questionnaire survey, during the formulation of which we took into account the results of our qualitative research. The sampling took place in March and April 2024, and we were able to evaluate the results of 83 respondents. The gender distribution of the respondents in the case of the in-depth interviews was exactly 50 percent, in the case of the questionnaires, 57% were men and 43% were women. Among the changes caused by digitization within their own professions, the interviewed men highlighted primarily the acceleration (news, data acquisition), secondly the variability in the field of newspapers, the "expansion of channels", the increased number of content producers and, at the same time, the loss of quality.

We also asked the journalists what they knew about the legal regulation of MI. Out of the 20 respondents, 18 people had not heard of it or were not familiar with it, 2 people showed greater awareness in this field, although they see that it is still very rudimentary and that its treatment is only at the level of problem statement and first guidelines, it is contradictory and there is no uniform regulation. The same group of questions led to the following result for the female interviewees participating in the study. Among the changes brought about by digitization, most people highlighted speed and increased accessibility. The field is changing significantly, the expansion of online platforms, easier data collection, immediacy appears as a goal. The motivation of content production changes, its focus shifts according to the interviewees, success is measured by achievements. However, the cold, profit-based thinking is contrasted with the normative journalistic ideal, which is thorough and looks into things, creative and authentic. AI helps and speeds up data collection, research work, and, where appropriate, ideation, but it cannot compete with an understanding and creative person - this is the opinion of several people. "Although the profession is digitized, it will never outgrow the human factor. People can add that extra something that makes the content more interesting. AI can help us, but it can-

not replace human work". Women see AI basically as a tool, they think of it as a kind of work support application.

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Gheorghe ANGHEL (University of Bucharest). *Safety, support, and protection: Unveiling the challenges faced by journalists in modern media*

Although social and technological progress might suggest a reduction in risks for journalists, the reality on the ground shows the opposite. Armed conflicts, social instability, political polarization, and accelerated digitalization have created an increasingly hostile environment for journalistic activity. International data reveal an alarming rise in violence against journalists: between 2021 and 2023, 154 journalists were killed, with 2023 marking a tragic record of 82 victims—the highest annual number in the past three decades. The only comparable year was 1999, with 76 cases recorded (Journalists Killed since 1992, n.d.).

While Romania has not reported such extreme cases recently, journalists continue to face various forms of pressure and intimidation. In 2021, the case of Italian journalist Lucia Goracci from RAI Television gained international attention after Romanian senator Diana Șoșoacă detained her against her will in her parliamentary office. Subsequently, Goracci and her crew were held by police at the senator's request (Italian TV Crew..., February 16, 2022). Perhaps the most important example is that of journalist Emilia Șercan, who faced a kompromat campaign after publishing an article accusing then-Prime Minister Nicolae Ciucă of plagiarizing his doctoral thesis. She received threats, and private photos were leaked online, including on adult websites. After reporting the incident to the authorities, the photos—originally submitted as evidence—ended up online, further undermining public trust in state institutions (U.S. Embassy in Romania, 2023). The lack of effective response from authorities continues to erode confidence in public institutions.

Findings from the Worlds of Journalism Study (2022-2023), based on a sample of 365 Romanian journalists, confirm these concerns. The most frequently reported risks experienced "often" or "very often" include "demeaning or hateful speech" (10.4%), "surveillance" (10.1%), and "public discrediting" (8.7%). Other threats, such as intimidation, online harassment, or legal pressure, were report-

ed less frequently but still significantly. These data highlight the predominance of psychological threats in today's media landscape.

Another concerning aspect is the lack of concrete support journalists receive when facing such pressures. According to the study, 94.4% of respondents did not receive support from government, and 83.7% reported no assistance from journalists' organization. NGOs also failed to offer support to 87.6% of participants, and 52.2% did not receive help even from fellow journalists. The only meaningful support came from their (own) news organizations (52.8%). In the absence of external support, journalists took protective measures themselves: 68.7% reported to have paid greater attention to verification, and 62% attended safety trainings. In contrast, only 1.4% benefited from government protection and 4.2% received legal protection.

This general climate contributes to high levels of professional anxiety: 42.2% of respondents expressed concerns about their physical safety, and 47.1% about their emotional and mental well-being. Even more troubling, 61.4% believe that those who harm journalists in Romania are usually not held accountable—a clear signal of impunity and institutional failure. Respondents with Bachelor's degree or equivalent were particularly vocal, reporting higher levels of concern for their well-being (over 20%) and greater perception of impunity (25.2%).

In conclusion, the results highlight not only an insecure professional environment but also an urgent need for systemic intervention—through protective policies, safety training, and real institutional support—so that journalism can fulfill its democratic mission freely and responsibly.

These findings are part of the Worlds of Journalism Study 2021–2023, third wave. The latest phase collected responses from 32,350 journalists in 75 countries, using an online questionnaire. In Romania, 365 responses were gathered.

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Nicoleta Elena APOSTOL (University of Bucharest). *Beyond technology: Are communication occupations ready for the knowledge economy? A gender perspective*

Journalism and programming are two occupational fields which formally are part of the knowledge sector. Findings suggest that the knowledge labor market – when taken as a whole – is characterized by more balanced gender em-

ployment patterns by comparison to the rest of the economic activities (Walby, 2011). Recent research shows that journalism continues to be marked by all traditional barriers in terms of gender patterns (e.g. De Vuyst, 2019); in computer programming – where women are to a higher degree numerically underrepresented – there are mixed findings, which reveal a greater gender inclusion (e.g. Klinger & Svensson, 2021). The study draws on original empirical material: a set of interviews with programmers (n=10 women, n=10 men), obtained between 2019-2021, and a batch of interviews with female journalists (n= 22), gathered in 2014-2015. All participants were based in Bucharest, Romania. Through a comparative approach, I extrapolated the common criteria that contribute to narrowing or to enhancing gender inequality, namely: (dis)embodiment, collaborative work, and horizontality.

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B

Alexandra BARDAN (University of Bucharest). *Behind the headline: How journalists see themselves*

This paper examines how Romanian journalists perceive their roles, professional status, and working conditions in a rapidly evolving media landscape, based on comparative data from the second and third waves of the Worlds of Journalism Study (WJS2: 2012–2016; WJS3: 2021–2023). With a focus on Romania's national samples (341 respondents in WJS2 and 367 in WJS3), the analysis reveals key transformations in journalists' demographics, employment patterns, and organizational contexts over the past decade.

Preliminary findings suggest a notable generational shift: the average age of journalists rose from 30.6 to 38 years, while the average professional experience doubled. Women continue to be overrepresented in the field, now comprising 65% of respondents, compared to 62% in WJS2. The education level has remained consistently high, with a large majority holding bachelor's or master's degrees. However, significant changes are observed in employment arrangements and newsroom hierarchies. While WJS2 indicated a predominantly permanent employment model, WJS3 shows a slight increase in temporary and freelance positions. Furthermore, the share of journalists in top editorial positions has declined, with most respondents indicating no leadership role. Shifts in media affiliation are also evident. Traditional print media's dominance

has diminished, while online media and alternative formats have become more prevalent. The diversity of newsroom job titles in WJS3 (47 different roles) also points to a more fragmented, hybridized professional environment.

These findings raise important questions about job security, professional autonomy, and the evolving identity of journalists in Romania. While some structural indicators (education, experience) suggest growing professionalization, others (employment status, editorial rank) may signal precariousness and diminishing influence. This mixed picture reflects broader global trends but also bears the imprint of local political, economic, and technological transformations. The paper contributes to the ongoing dialogue about journalism under pressure by offering an empirical snapshot of a profession navigating between legacy roles and emergent challenges. It emphasizes the value of longitudinal comparative data in making sense of how journalists see themselves and their work "behind the headline."

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Daniele BATTISTA (University of Salerno). *Lights and shadows in the digital communicative world: The age of AI-driven political disinformation*

The contemporary technological environment has been transformed by the rapid and consistent spread of artificial intelligence (AI), arousing great enthusiasm in academia and beyond. This progress has triggered a vibrant debate on its effects, raising essential questions that require careful multi-centred analysis. In particular, the spread of disinformation in the media and political communication is one of the most pressing challenges. The integration of AI in these areas has both advantages and risks: on the one hand, it can improve efficiency in the distribution of information and increase the transparency of institutions; on the other hand, it can be exploited to spread fake news and manipulate public opinion. It will examine how AI-based technologies can be used to create and disseminate false content and how such practices influence public perception and democratic debate. The research methodology will follow a deduc-

tive approach, based on a detailed analysis of narratives, representations and expectations related to AI and disinformation. Concrete case studies, regulatory policies and counter strategies adopted in different national and international contexts will be analysed. This research aims to contribute to the understanding of the complex dynamics related to disinformation in the media and political communication. The critical analysis will provide an innovative perspective and a comprehensive picture of the different connections and impacts arising from the use of AI, with the aim of developing effective strategies to counter disinformation and promote transparent and accountable political communication.

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Valentina BOUREANU (Universitatea din București). *Comunicare de branduri naționale. Studiu de caz: la românească*

Întrebări de cercetare: dacă avea Louis Vuitton dreptul să folosească ia românească în colecția lansată de curând; dacă a fost îndreptățită reacția de revoltă a organizațiilor din România; dacă a fost eficient și suficient modul în care organizațiile românești au reacționat.

Obiectivele studiului: identificarea publicurilor din România și analiza modului în care acestea au reacționat la folosirea iei românești de către Louis Vuitton; identificarea deținătorului dreptului de proprietate asupra obiectului vestimentar; analiza identității de brand a Casei Louis Vuitton pentru a determina ideea specifică, valorile și publicul țintă; analiza modului în care Louis Vuitton a respectat principiile specifice teoriei brandingului și a reacției sale la obiectiile din România.

Metodologia cercetării

Ipoteza cercetării: folosind-o ca idee a unei colecții recente de haine, Louis Vuitton nu a încălcat drepturile de proprietate asupra cămășii populare românești din Mărginimea Sibiului, atâta vreme cât deținătorii acesteia nu au

protejat-o printr-o marcă înregistrată la OSIM. Am aplicat, astfel, analiza de conținut calitativă și cantitativă pe un corpus (documente de presă) reprezentativ și suficient referitor la reacția publicurilor direct implicate: organizații românești și brandul Louis Vuitton.

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C

Francisco López CANTOS (University of Jaume I). *The drone warfare. Fact-checking, fake-pictures and necropolitics*

In this paper, we deal with the use and effects on press news around aerial images provided by unmanned aerial systems in conflict environments and, in particular, with the verification work that has been carried out to determine their validity, or in broad terms, their "objectivity" and relationship with "reality". To this end, we have selected a sample of verification reports that detect and analyse the dissemination of false images in the press recorded or related by drones, in order to characterise the type of manipulation that has been carried out in the pictures and the procedures of detection used. We conclude that the use of this technology is becoming a perceived threat to public opinion as a result of its notoriety in the news, which currently focuses mainly on its use in military conflicts, overshadowing its usefulness for civilian and peaceful purposes.

Francisca CARVALHO (Universidade Nova de Lisboa) & Alexandre DUARTE (Universidade Nova de Lisboa). *Femvertising in All Shapes and Sizes: Exploring the Determinants of Success for a Femvertising Campaign*

This paper explores different scholarly perspectives on femvertising and analyzes two advertising campaigns from prominent lingerie brands, namely VS Collective by Victoria's Secret and Aerie Real by American Eagle Outfitters. It

seeks to discern the factors that determine the success of an advertising campaign in terms of promoting social change and driving sales for the company. The results show that a key marker of authenticity, and therefore a major determinant of a campaign's success, is the consistency of advertising messages with the corporate practices, products and social initiatives by the brand. Whereas Victoria's Secret's efforts to be more inclusive were met with skepticism due to inconsistencies between the campaign's message and the brand's established identity, Aerie's dedication and commitment to feminist values generated immense consumer support, loyalty and, consequently, revenue.

Narcis CRUCIAN (SNSPA). Percepțiile studenților români în legătură cu fenomenul fake news în era social media

În era digitală, social media joacă un rol crucial în viața studenților, influențând modul în care aceștia accesează și interpretează informațiile. Acest articol analizează modul în care social media, fenomenul fake news, bias-urile cognitive și utilizarea algoritmilor și a inteligenței artificiale se intersectează în eforturile de combatere a dezinformării. Mai precis, articolul arată ce consecințe negative pot avea acestea asupra tinerilor studenți, cum evoluția noilor tehnologii a simplificat difuzarea fake news, ce bias-uri cognitive amplifică vulnerabilitatea la fake news, distorsionând astfel înțelegerea realității și cât de importantă este alfabetizarea media în contextul creșterii rezilienței publicului. Literatura de specialitate (Centrul Român de Politici Europene, 2021; Mandache & Ivan, 2022; Centrul Euro-Atlantic pentru Reziliență, 2023) sugerează că rezidenții din mediul rural, tinerii, persoanele în vârstă, persoanele cu dizabilități și cei mai puțin educați sunt tipurile de public cele mai vulnerabile la dezinformare. Având în vedere acest lucru, autorul a ales un eșantion de conveniență format din studenți pentru a investiga dacă aceștia sunt într-adevăr vulnerabili la dezinformare sau nu. Mai mult, autorul alege să compare două categorii diferite de studenți pentru a investiga dacă profilul urmat (real sau uman) influențează percepția acestora asupra fenomenului fake news. La baza acestui studiu a stat un ghid de interviu care a fost aplicat unui număr de 20 studenți (10 studenți cu profil real și 10 studenți cu profil uman). Rezultatele acestui studiu au demonstrat că studenții cunosc motivele din spatele răspândirii fake news și a dezinformării, știu că rețelele sociale amplifică substanțial gradul de expunere și de răspândire al acestor două și sunt conștienți de efecte negative pe care le-au produs la nivelul societății precum și individual. De asemenea, studenții nu cunosc conceptul de „citirea laterală”, marea majoritate verifică informațiile numai după ce le citesc, dar folosesc alte tehnici de verificare a informațiilor.

Întrebări de cercetare:

ÎC1. Cum văd tinerii dezinformarea și ce aspecte problematice asociază dezinformării?

ÎC2. Ce tehnici de verificare a informațiilor cunosc și aplică tinerii? Este „citire laterală” una dintre acestea? Ce alte tehnici menționează aceștia?

ÎC3. Ce bias-uri cognitive apar, la nivelul tinerilor, atunci când se confruntă cu informații din social media?

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D

Georgeta DRULĂ (University of Bucharest). *Artificial Intelligence: Topics Covered on Romanian News Websites*

This study examines the interest in artificial intelligence in Romanian news websites. Articles were collected from the Google.com search engine, on the News tab using the keyword “inteligența artificială” from January 2023 to February 2024. All collected data were scraped using SERP API tools and have the Search Engine Page Results (SERP) format: articles headlines, news website names, publication dates, and web addresses.

The relationship between AI and journalism has been studied from many perspectives but the main preoccupation is connected to the influence of AI authorship in journalism (Lermann Henestrosa, Greving, and Kimmerle, 2023). Nevertheless, numerous AI tools generate visual multimedia content that could be used in news production. Also, artificial intelligence (AI) tools and technologies can be involved at different stages for news production and support quality journalism (Opdahl et al., 2023) but they transform the editorial process and invoke a new media business model (Underwood 2018; Parratt-Fernández, Rodríguez-Pallares and Pérez-Serrano, 2024).

Mixed methods were applied to a corpus of news articles extracted from Google News with a web scrapper, such as sentiment analysis, semantic/text network analysis, and thematic analysis. Descriptive statistical methods were also applied to the data to provide the trends.

Findings are on 448 articles collected from 36 news websites in the process of data scraping. Applying the thematic analysis and key points we found four themes of interest published in the Romanian news sites about artificial intelligence. On the same corpus, we applied sentiment analysis to identify the tone in which the articles were written.

The conclusions of this study show that a corpus of published articles treated both the Romanian situation related to artificial intelligence and the international aspects. Implementation of AI in different environments and sectors of activi-

ty, interviews with Romanian specialists who offer opinions and clarifications on various aspects and perspectives related to AI, and applications of AI technologies are the most frequently encountered topic in the articles from Romanian news websites.

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F

Marion FABRE (Université Lumière Lyon 2). *L'utilisation de l'IAG : inclusion et réussite universitaire*

L'étude interroge les effets de l'intelligence artificielle générative (IAG) sur les dynamiques de réussite estudiantine dans les universités françaises. En s'appuyant sur une double enquête (quantitative et qualitative), il met en lumière des usages variés, prudents et massifs de l'IAG par les étudiants, perçus tantôt comme un outil de soutien, tantôt comme un levier d'inclusion. Loin d'une substitution à l'apprentissage, l'IAG apparaît comme un outil complémentaire favorisant autonomie, structuration des savoirs et confiance académique. L'étude révèle : (1) une tension entre régulations institutionnelles défensives et pratiques étudiantes déjà intégrées, parfois marquées par une personnalisation de l'IA ; (2) l'urgence de développer une pédagogie critique et réflexive de l'IA, afin de co-construire un usage éthique et didactique. L'IAG, souvent envisagée comme menace, s'impose ici comme une opportunité pour redéfinir les contours de l'acte d'apprendre et repenser les conditions d'une réussite universitaire plus inclusive.

Remerciements. Le projet de recherche «L'impact de l'intelligence artificielle (IA) sur les pratiques professionnelles dans l'enseignement universitaire de communication et médias» (IACOM) bénéficie du soutien financier de l'Agence universitaire de la Francophonie dans le cadre de l'«Appel à projets 2023 - Soutien aux Équipes de recherche en Europe Centrale et Orientale - SER-ECO».

Maximiliano FERNÁNDEZ FERNÁNDEZ (Universidad Rey Juan Carlos), Sebastiano NUCERA (Università degli Studi di Messina), Carlos FERNÁNDEZ ALAMEDA (Universidad Rey Juan Carlos). *Artificial Intelligence in the classroom and in virtual environments. Applications and critical positions*

The controversy between techno-optimists and technological pessimists or technocritics acquires currently greater magnitude and virulence due to the intensity of the changes that the application of Artificial Intelligence entails.

But it has a long historical trajectory in which both classical and modern critical sociologists and innovative figures who have contributed and defended great technological advances.

Data and arguments are presented related to the economic interests in e-learning, which generates millions of euros and thousands of jobs, with a growth estimated for 2025 by Forbes at 325 billion dollars; related with the economic effort of public administrations to promote digital development, the evidence of the digital divide between the info-rich and the info-poor, etc.

And international organizations such as UNESCO, which supports the potential of humanizing technologies in the perspective of the Education Agenda 2030, ensuring sustainable development, inclusion and equity ("AI for all"), protecting human rights in the framework of collaboration between man and machine.

This paper aims to present a state of the art and to appeal data and applications that, beyond the favorable or unfavorable narrative, allow us to measure and assess the current consequences of the irruption of AI in education and other virtual environments.

The conclusion is that the development of AI is inevitable and unstoppable, and that all efforts made by international organizations, social sciences and responsible policies must be aimed at controlling its advances and effects or its impacts and consequences for that our world doesn't become even more runaway or unbridled.

Andrada FISCUTEAN (University of Bucharest). *The pressure to inform - internal factors. The workday realities of journalists*

Journalists face a multitude of challenges in their mission of informing the public. This research analyzes data from the third wave (2021-2023) of the Worlds of Journalism study, in an effort to understand how professional norms, organizational structures, and individual characteristics influence journalistic practices.

The results show that while many internal influences have remained stable compared to the second wave of the same study (2014-2015), some shifts have indeed occurred. According to the data collected through online questionnaires, journalistic ethics continues to be the most influential factor, followed by access to information resources and editorial policy, with the latter climbing in perceived importance compared to the second wave, which suggests a grow-

ing institutional control over content production. This study also shows that personal values and peer influence have declined in perceived relevance.

We observe differences in perception across gender, editorial roles, as well as education: journalists with higher education levels, for instance, are more likely to emphasize ethical considerations and recognize commercial pressures. There are also differences between media organizations, depending on their funding structure, business model, and level of editorial independence.

This analysis points to a complex relation between professional ideals and day-to-day realities. While ethics remains central to journalists, factors such as rising economic and managerial pressures may challenge their autonomy.

G

Gabriela GAVRILESCU, Georgiana UDREA, & Diana MUNTEANU (SNSPA). *Dependența de social media și efectele sale asupra tinerilor din România*

În contextul digital curent, social media reprezintă o componentă esențială a vieții cotidiene pentru tinerii din România. Platformele sociale precum Facebook, Instagram și TikTok se bucură de popularitate în rândul tinerilor, fiind utilizate pentru a comunica, a se informa și a se distra, influențând modul în care interacționează, își gestionează relațiile și timpul liber.

Prezenta cercetare investighează efectele dependenței de social media asupra nativilor din Generația Z. Prin intermediul cadrului explicativ furnizat de teoria „utilizării și recompense”, studiul explorează percepțiile tinerilor asupra beneficiilor, cât și a riscurilor asociate cu rețelele sociale (Lu & Lin, 2022), pentru a oferi o perspectivă asupra impactului pe care social media îl are asupra sănătății mentale, relațiilor interpersonale și performanței academice a tinerilor români. Cercetarea a fost realizată printr-o abordare calitativă, având interviul semi-structurat, în profunzime ca instrument de cercetare, aplicat pe un grup de conveniență alcătuit din tineri cu vârste cuprinse între 19 și 25 de ani.

Tinerii intervievați au confirmat că utilizarea social media le influențează semnificativ stilul de viață. În ceea ce privește efectele pozitive percepute, platformele sociale facilitează menținerea relațiilor sociale, accesul rapid la informații și posibilitatea de a se exprima liber. Au fost semnalate și riscuri asociate utilizării acestora, frecvent menționată fiind dezvoltarea unor comportamente adictive (cyberaddiction), care pot conduce la izolarea de lumea reală, scăderea stimei de sine și experiențe de tip cyberbullying (Aparisi et al., 2023). De asemenea, fenomenul de comparație socială, augmentat de imaginile ideale promovate pe aceste platforme, poate avea efecte negative asupra sănătății mentale a tinerilor, determinând dificultăți de adaptare socială și anxietate (O'Day & Heimberg, 2021).

Concluziile acestui studiu relevă necesitatea dezvoltării de politici publice și educaționale care să promoveze utilizarea echilibrată a social media, în vederea diminuării riscurilor asociate și îmbunătățirii stării de bine a tinerilor. Este im-

portant ca tinerii să fie educați în direcția gestionării timpului petrecut online și conștientizării efectelor potențiale rezultate în urma utilizării excesive a platformelor sociale.

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Gabriela GAVRILESCU, Alexandra NEIDONI (SNSPA). *Tendințe actuale în combaterea fenomenului știrilor false*

În noul ecosistem informațional, știrile false au devenit un cuvânt-cheie folosit pentru a descrie termenul de dezinformare, mai ales în mediul digital (Aïmeur et al., 2023; Shu & Liu, 2019). Lumea digitală a căpătat noi dimensiuni ca urmare a apariției și proliferării platformelor sociale. Prin intermediul acestora materialele false se propagă cu ușurință, fiind distribuite și redistribuite de publicul larg, preluate ad litteram și determinând, adesea, sentimente de panică și revoltă (Olan et al., 2024). Deși dezbaterea asupra acestui fenomen a devenit multidisciplinară (un subiect de actualitate pentru cercetători din diverse domenii precum antropologi, sociologi sau politologi), literatura actuală nu epuizează complexitatea problemelor legate de știrile false. În acest context, întrebări precum: „Care sunt cele mai importante efecte ale știrilor false?” „Cum putem combate eficient fenomenul știrilor false?” rămân deschise și necesită clarificări suplimentare. Aceste întrebări pot fi văzute ca un punct de plecare pentru prezenta lucrare, al cărei scop este să analizeze tendințele actuale privind modalitățile de combatere a fenomenului. Prima secțiune va prezenta pe scurt cele mai comune direcții teoretice în cercetarea actuală asupra știrilor false, urmând a fi evidențiate diversele afirmații concurente privind efectele știrilor false, concentrându-se pe cele mai recente descoperiri din literatură care discută despre patologiile comunicaționale din sfera online. Ultima parte a lucrării va aborda modul în care oamenii procesează și gestionează informațiile pe care le întâlnesc, indiferent dacă acestea sunt adevărate sau false. Acest demers se bazează pe convingerea că numai prin furnizarea unei înțelegeri mai profunde a fenomenului știrilor false vom putea găsi soluții relevante pentru modelarea politicilor publice cu scopul de a ajuta oamenii să facă diferența între știri adevărate, documentate și știri care prezintă fapte false, evenimente scoase din context sau prezentate într-un unghi care generează o imagine total sau cel puțin parțial falsă a realității.

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Mihai GAVRILESCU (SNSPA), Georgiana UDREA (SNSPA), Ilinca LAZĂR (SNSPA). *Gamificarea digitală. Perspective ale Generației Z asupra utilizării Duolingo și Snapchat*

În contextul digital actual, Generația Z utilizează intens aplicațiile mobile pentru învățare și integrare socială (Hernandez-de-Menendez et al., 2020; Kullolli & Trebicka, 2023). Tot mai prezentă în dezvoltarea acestor instrumente, gamificarea reprezintă integrarea mecanicilor de joc în aplicații non-ludice pentru a motiva și implica utilizatorii (Saxena & Mishra, 2021; Stylos & Vassiliadis, 2023). Prezenta cercetare explorează modul în care elementele de gamificare din Duolingo și Snapchat influențează experiența de învățare și comunicare online a tinerilor din România și Germania. Studiul propune o abordare calitativă, bazată pe interviuri în profunzime, obiectivul său principal fiind evaluarea comparativă a perspectivelor nativilor Generației Z din România și Germania asupra elementelor de gamificare din aplicațiile Duolingo și Snapchat, cu scopul de a identifica potențiale diferențe între motivațiile și practicile de utilizare. Accentul cade pe motivele utilizării, efectele elementelor de gamificare asupra motivației, implicării și îmbunătățirii experienței de utilizare viitoare. Rezultatele arată că tinerii utilizează Duolingo pentru învățarea/aprofundarea limbilor străine și Snapchat pentru menținerea conexiunilor sociale. Elementele de gamificare, precum streak-urile și recompensele, sunt apreciate pentru capacitatea lor de a crește motivația și implicarea utilizatorilor. Participanții la studiu remarcă asupra potențialului acestor elemente de a le menține interesul, a-i motiva să atingă obiective personale și a le permite monitorizarea progresului zilnic. Ei sugerează îmbunătățirea personalizării și complexității acestor elemente pentru a spori și mai mult angajamentul. Înțelegerea aprofundată a acestor aspecte poate ajuta dezvoltatorii să optimizeze interfețele și structura aplicațiilor, îmbunătățind astfel experiența utilizatorilor. Datele furnizate de cercetarea prezentă au aplicabilitate practică sporită în direcția ghidării dezvoltatorilor de aplicații în crearea unor experiențe de utilizare mai atractive și eficiente, oferirea de suport științific pentru instituțiile educaționale în elaborarea de ghiduri privind implementarea gamificării în procesele de învățare și creșterea conștientizării impactului acestor aplicații asupra membrilor Generației Z.

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Mihai GAVRILESCU (SNSPA). *Prietenul meu digital apropiat: Interacțiuni și relații parasociale cu inteligența artificială*

Odată cu apariția și proliferarea noilor algoritmi avansați de procesare a limbajului natural (eng. NLP), se deschid noi oportunități de cercetare în direcția înțelegerii nuanțelor relațiilor om-IA (Barreda-Ángeles & Hartmann, 2022; Hoffner & Bond, 2022). Modele explicative, precum interacțiunile parasociale (PSI) și relațiile parasociale (PSR), pot oferi, corect înțelese și revizuite, cadre interpretative viabile pentru decodificarea dinamicilor atitudinale și comportamentale care apar în timpul și după utilizarea tehnologiilor bazate pe inteligență artificială (IA) (Yang et al., 2022). Prezenta propunere de cercetare investighează potențialul noilor instrumente IA de a induce manifestări PSI/PSR. Accentul este pus pe identificarea determinantilor individuali care acționează ca predictor pentru dezvoltarea unor astfel de legături, precum și în ce măsură instrumentele de măsurare actuale pot fi adaptate la specificitățile noilor tipuri de avatare media. Design-ul de cercetare este unul calitativ și exploratoriu, bazat pe grupuri de discuții care investighează experiențele personale și percepțiile utilizatorilor care interacționează cu sisteme IA avansate. Datele astfel colectate pot oferi informații detaliate și bogate despre natura PSR în relație cu entitățile IA, evidențiind dimensiunile emoționale, cognitive și sociale ale acestor interacțiuni. Ulterior, studiul propune utilizarea metodei cantitative a chestionarelor auto-administrate, având ca scop capturarea tendințelor și tiparelor răspândite în interacțiunile utilizatorilor cu IA. Această abordare duală permite o explorare amănunțită atât a profunzimii, cât și a amplitudinii fenomenului. Rezultatele anticipează existența unor tipare de trăsături de personalitate care pot duce la o incidență ridicată a dezvoltării dinamicilor PSI/PSR, confirmând potențialul acestor sisteme de a transcende rolurile tradiționale și de a favoriza relații complexe și durabile cu utilizatorii. Astfel de date științifice pot ghida cercetări viitoare către înțelegerea mecanismelor complexe ce guvernează acest tip de interacțiuni și propune soluții de optimizare a sistemelor informatice pentru a preveni simptomele de devianță clinică în urma utilizării IA.

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Eugen ISTODOR (Universitatea din București). *Cum s-a întâmplat ca Inteligența Artificială „să fure” jurnalismului mitologia*

Credința în obiectivitate, precizie, predictibilitate, moralitate face parte din mitologia jurnalismului, iar Inteligența Artificială, în primul rând, aceste atribute le-a impus public, ca fiind ale sale. În cercetarea de față ne propunem să analizăm câteva referințe românești clasice din domeniul jurnalisticii și să stabilim astfel numitorul comun, corpusul de principii al mass media (Manualul de jurnalism, coord. Coman, 2009; Introducere în sistemul mass media, Coman, 2016; Introducere în jurnalism, Agnes, 2011; Presa scrisă. O introducere critică, Keeble, 2009; Sociologia mass-media, Rieffel, 2008; Istoria jurnalismului și a publicității în România, Petcu, 2007; Jurnalistul universal, Randall, 2007).

În partea a doua, vom urmări „confruntarea” explicită între principiile enunțate/ definițiile mass media și cele ale Inteligenței Artificiale (referire la ChatGPT, în special). Vom dobândi un parcurs istoric și o descriere sociologică a meseriei de jurnalist, dar și o caracterizare succintă a comportamentului generațional al publicului. Criza jurnalismului, odată cu apariția tehnologiei performante de machine learning și Inteligență Artificială, va fi observată printr-o descriere a reconfigurării economice (Brynjolfsson și McAfee, 2011) și una a rescrierii tehnologice a nevoilor sociale (O’Gieblyn, 2021). Nu în ultimul rând, vom privi spre fenomenul fake news și spre relația acestuia cu mijloacele tehnologice de fabricare (troti, boți, etc.) a acestuia. Mitologia mass media și practicile jurnalistice au primit o lovitură și în această privință. Fake news-ul nu doar se insinuează și creează evenimente (alegerea președintelui Donald Trump, Brexit), dar cu adevărat duce la diminuarea discernământului publicului. Putem să ne întrebăm dacă Inteligența Artificială poate fi un arbitru nu doar în acest bombardament informațional greu de disecat, dar și în recreerea încrederii în informație.

Roland-Mihai ÎMPUȘCATU (University of Bucharest). *The Revolution of Artificial Creativity - A technological review*

This study aims to provide an overview of the most widely used artificial intelligence (AI) and generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) tools on the market. It analyzes the impact that emerging technology applications can have on the field of communication through a detailed review of how they can contribute to streamlining and augmenting communication processes. The study provides an applied review of applications such as Midjourney, Runway, ChatGPT, Dalle-E2 or Elevenlabs and offers a pragmatic view on how they can be integrated into the workflow of communication campaigns. The emergence of ChatGPT in November 2022 marked the beginning of a new era for humankind, and the communications industry is among the most affected across the globe, with professionals constantly having to adapt to the new changes offered by these emerging technologies. Although the use of AI is still in its infancy, it is being rapidly adopted by companies, with 90% of them currently developing AI-based strategies. In this context, understanding how technology applications work and what are their capabilities is becoming vital for the communications industry. The objective of the study is to reveal the main ways of use and applicability of these technologies in the communication market. The study aims to answer the following research questions: (1) "What are the best ways of integrating AI capabilities in advertising?" and (2) "what is the usefulness of integrating AI and GenAI in the process of communication campaigns?". The review is compared with case studies from advertising and public relations, where human creativity is already being augmented by AI in successful communication campaigns. In 2023, 8.3% of all Cannes Lions winning campaigns used GenAI in their production.

M

Antonia MATEI (University of Bucharest). *From watchdog to guide: How journalists see themselves in society*

Purpose: In an era characterized by widespread misinformation and overlapping crises, public confidence in journalistic institutions continues to decline annually. Within this complex informational landscape, the role of journalists and media organizations remains paramount in ensuring the dissemination of true, precise, and relevant information. As journalism faces numerous challenges, analyzing and understanding journalistic roles is an important step in strengthening the press's position as a structural pillar of society.

Design/methodology/approach: This presentation is based on data from the Worlds of Journalism Study 2023. The third wave of the project collected responses of more than 32,350 journalists in 75 countries. In Romania, the sample consisted of 365 respondents from different types of media. A standardized questionnaire, translated into multiple languages, was used, thus ensuring consistency of the results. The survey focused on themes such as journalists' safety,

editorial freedom, journalistic roles, influences on news production journalism, risks, and uncertainties.

Findings: The Romanian journalists have undergone a major redefinition of their professional identity compared to the initial waves of the World Journalism Study in 2007 and 2016. The disinformation phenomenon and the challenges of today's world have led to a reconsideration of the classical roles of presenting things as they are and being a detached observer (assumed by Romanian journalists in 2016). They now place traditional journalistic values in the background and take on more socially and community-engaged functions, moving toward two newly introduced, proactive roles – countering misinformation (85.5% of the journalists) and shining a light on society's problems (81.5% of the journalists). These new roles are deeply rooted in the recent crises which have attacked the very essence of the profession, undermining the role of journalism and also negatively impacting public trust in the press.

Another role that requires active involvement from journalists and, at the same time a recurrent one for Romanian journalists, is that of educating the public as 77.7% of respondents identified this as a significant role. Taking into account the rise of fake news and the challenges of the modern media, for Romanian journalists educating the public is a crucial responsibility, as it plays a key role in encouraging analytical thinking and combating misinformation.

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Ramona MARINACHE (University of Bucharest), Valentina MARINESCU, (University of Bucharest). *The future of reading in the age of Artificial Intelligence*

The importance of reading (on paper) in maintaining and regaining health has been studied for the past few decades. The aim of this presentation is to stress the future possible direction of reading in the age of Artificial intelligence.

Our research questions were:

RQ1: What are the positive effects of reading for health and wellbeing?

RQ2. What is the difference of the impact that reading on digital devices has on health as compared with traditional reading of books?

As methodology we used a literature review of the existing studies.

Our analysis showed that reading fiction (from short stories to novels) increases life expectancy, improves cognition (irrespective of age), improves the

behavior of children (they are attentive in classes and less aggressive). Reading improves language and thinking (and this is why people are able to describe their symptoms to their physician). Also, reading reduces stress; reading increases neurological wellness and thus is linked with a lower risk of developing neurological problems, and reading shortens recovery of health. Now, in the age of the fourth industrial revolution reading habits are changing in unimaginable ways. Reading can be done on devices that can keep track of our speed of reading, can resume a long text or can read for us while we are engaged in other activities.

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Valentina MARINESCU (University of Bucharest) & Ramona MARINACHE (University of Bucharest). *The Future of Energy Sustainability and Artificial Intelligence. An overview*

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development is a document developed by United Nations as a 'blueprint', as they call it, for the present and future of people and the planet. Assumed through this agenda by all UN member states there are 17 goals that comprise all human existence in its social and environmental interdependences, from economic well-being to gender equality, from individual production and use of energy to industry and economic growth.

The aim of the presentation will start from the 7th goal of the agenda - "affordable and clean energy" - in order to analyze the social sustainability of clean electric energy in the Artificial Intelligence domain.

The research questions of the presentation are:

RQ1. Is it possible social sustainability of clean electric energy in the Artificial Intelligence domain?

RQ2. What are the main consequences of the shifting from oil and gas based production to 'renewable resources' for the advancement of the Artificial Intelligence?

We made a literature review of the articles published in the last years and we analyze the social chains of interdependences determined by each of the two types of electric energy production, from the exploitation of resources used to produce the electric energy to the moment of the energy consumption by households and individuals.

The conclusion will stress the possible social futures based on the variable "clean energy consumption" for the progress of Artificial Intelligence.

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Antonio MOMOC (University of Bucharest). *AI and Modern Radio: The Curious Case of the Alex Ionescu Project at ProFM*

The AI revolution has led radio stations and advertising agencies to use voice software to replace actors or radio DJs for presenting radio shows or audio advertising clips. The radio of the future appears to be a station that delivers digitally customized news and programs for each user based on their personal profile.

ProFM has launched the first Romanian-language radio show presented by an AI DJ. In Romania, FM radio is experiencing a slight decline in popularity, with older audiences primarily listening on traditional devices. ProFM introduced the "Alex Ionescu project", Romania's first AI DJ, aimed at attracting younger audiences and reducing production costs, even though it paradoxically requires a human team. Like the main character in F. Scott Fitzgerald's story "The Curious Case of Benjamin Button", the ProFM team seeks a "Button effect" to rejuvenate the station by drawing in younger listeners. ProFM integrates AI software and GPT technology into FM radio by generating innovative audio content, enhancing listener interaction through advanced chatbots that provide personalized experiences and real-time responses. The technical issues with intonation in Romanian language of the AI DJ led the ProFM team to hire more human editors to correct pronunciation errors, giving the bot more fluency and credibility. In conclusion, through comprehensive 360-degree projects, GPT plays a crucial role in modernizing radio, transforming it into a more dynamic, interactive, and adaptable medium that meets the needs and lifestyles of radio listeners.

Mădălina MORARU (University of Bucharest). *The role of AI tools in raising the level of efficiency in visual creativity*

The main purpose of this study is to analyze the extent to which AI tools are used by art directors, web designers, and graphic designers in advertising agencies to effectively convey the big idea (message) of a campaign. The challenge of this research lies in understanding the relationship between the skills of art directors and the use of AI tools.

The main research questions refer to: How does the use of AI tools impact the creative decisions of art directors in advertising agencies? What are the key reasons for incorporating AI visual tools in a campaign? How can we evaluate the efficiency of visual creative professionals when utilizing AI tools?

The research method intended to address these questions is qualitative: the semi-structured interview accompanied by thematic analysis. The interviewees belong to Gen Z and are employees in advertising agencies, either local or global, all located in Bucharest. In terms of experience, the respondents are still juniors, aged between 1 and 4 years, as it is intriguing to understand how they link their creative work with technology. However, it is particularly significant to investigate how they perceive the threat posed by the progress of AI in the creative industry.

To fulfil the objectives of this paper, I conducted 10 interviews with junior creative teams from advertising agencies between May 4th and June 20th. The current research is ongoing as I aim to compare the perspectives of Gen Z with those of Millennials.

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Bogdan OPREA (University of Bucharest). *Safety and media: Reporting during the COVID pandemic, amidst hate speech, public discrediting, and surveillance*

The main threats to Romanian journalists are manifested through hate speech and humiliation, surveillance and public discrediting, according to data from The Worlds of Journalism Study 2021-2023. Over 1 in 10 Romanian journalists state that, during this period, marked as a period of COVID-19 pandemic, they

were "often" and "very often" victims of "demeaning or hateful speech" 10.4%; mean = 1.96; standard deviations = 1.1) and of "surveillance" (10.1%; m = 1.84; s = 1.136) and almost 9% (8.7%; m = 1.82; s = 1.061), of "public discrediting". These actions, perceived as "often" and "very often", have the highest values among journalists who do not have a management role and those in middle management. Men (m) report being "often" and "very often" victims of the three types of actions that endanger their security more often than women (w), "public discrediting" (m = 5.8%; w = 4.9%), "surveillance" (m = 5.8%; w = 4.3%) and, respectively, "demeaning or hateful speech" (m = 5.4%; w = 4.9%). Journalists with a Master's degree or equivalent (M) are more likely to report being victims of this three types of actions than those with a Bachelor's degree or equivalent (B) or those that have completed only high school (H), as "demeaning or hateful speech" (M = 6%; B = 2.2%; H = 0.8%), "public discrediting" (M = 4.7%; B = 2.8%; H = 0.3%) and, respectively, "surveillance" (M = 4.1%; B = 4.4%; H = 0.5%), as well as those who have completed a formal education or specialized training in journalism compared to those who do not have such training, "demeaning or hateful speech" (yes = 8.2%; no = 2.2%), "surveillance" (yes = 8%; no = 2.2%) and, respectively, "public discrediting" (yes = 7.1%; no = 1.6%). In some cases (3.3%), pressure on journalists also manifested in the form of "legal actions", the intention of which can easily be considered a form of pressure and intimidation. The data is based on the research The Worlds of Journalism Study 2021-2023, which is in its third multi-annual edition, and was carried out in 117 countries. The fieldwork was carried out between October 2022 and September 2023, and, from a methodological perspective, used a standard questionnaire, which was applied online to 365 journalists from Romania. The conceptual framework of the study was build on two theoretical features: an understanding of journalism as a discursive institution (general perspective), and the modeling of key areas of risk and uncertainty in journalism (specific approach). How at the heart of this discourse lies journalists' perception of risk, as well as the institutional uncertainty they produce, the study focused on the sources of risk (areas of threats), the forms of its manifestation (manifestation of threats) and perceptions of risk (areas of uncertainty) (The Worlds of Journalism Study 2021-2023).

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The Worlds of Journalism Study 2021-2023. <https://worldsofjournalism.org/conceptual-framework/>

P

Manuela PREOTEASA (University of Bucharest). *Disinformation in social media: Recurrent Narratives and Techniques Content Analysis of 600 Social Media Posts distributed in Three Languages*

This paper focuses on three main disinformation themes - migration, climate change, and health - and aims to identify the most frequently recurring disinformation practices related to these narratives and the most common techniques

used to simulate truth. The research questions involve understanding how these narratives are constructed: through digital manipulation, by embedding partly true information in a fake or missing context, or by combining false and true elements.

The corpus consists of 600 claims distributed on social media in three languages - French, Romanian, and English (German claims are also available but not included in this analysis). These claims were selected and filtered using technological tools developed by the AI4Trust (www.ai4trust.eu) project. The project's social correction module generates verdicts based on human fact-checking, which then serve as the basis for labeling the claims as false, partly false, or containing pieces of truth placed in a missing context.

The comparison of recurrent narratives and techniques across different topics and languages will rely on the Wardle's Venn Diagram (2021, 2023) to identify and define models of recurrences in relation to the disinformation taxonomy and characteristics.

Key conceptual framework:

Wardle, C. (2021, August 3). Understanding Information disorder. First Draft. <https://firstdraftnews.org/long-form-article/understanding-information-disorder/>

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Raluca PETRE (Ovidius University of Constanța). *The European Broadcasting Union and Artificial Intelligence*

The European Broadcasting Union is the largest association of public service media providers, a large nongovernmental organisation that assists, represents, and sets the infrastructural basis of cooperation for its constituents. In this paper I address multiple uses of AI within the workings of the association, pointing to the novel ways PSMs innovate and cooperate around a convergent understanding of information as a public good. The research is based on a neo-institutional understanding of a sector as a unit of analysis and considering the organisational ecosystem with its full explanatory value (Powell & DiMaggio, 1991).

More specifically, in this paper I approach three EBU in-house innovations that have AI components, but that nevertheless keep the human editorial function at the core of activities and choices. I will discuss EuroVOX - language processing toolkit, incorporating AI technologies; PEACH - Personalisation for each, a PSM-oriented recommender system, which combines classic recommender algorithms (content-based filtering to find similar content and collaborative filtering to find similar users) with a novel mechanism to recommend diverse content, and A European Perspective - an online news exchange / connecting a continent through trusted news that incorporates the AI tools described above.

The fundamental dynamic of journalistic information has always been structured around exchange and cooperation within EBU since its early days. At the same time, language and technological barriers made the net volume of news exchanged to be quite low until recently. Nevertheless, given the incorporation of AI in the news exchange activities made it possible that hundred of thousands of European citizens have access to European news on a daily basis via their PSMs news sites.

It is interesting to observe that “A European Perspective” was proposed and financed as a European project by the European Commission, one of the traditional adversaries of PSM as a counter market institutional structuration.

Iasmina PETROVICI (West University of Timișoara) & Corina SÎRB (West University of Timișoara). *Efficiency vs Authenticity: Using artificial intelligence apps for advertising design purposes*

What are the conveniences and the limitations of using artificial intelligence in advertising design? Can artificial intelligence completely replace the work of an advertising designer? Is artificial intelligence capable of creativity and originality in advertising design? These are just several questions that lie at the basis of our study. Using interdisciplinary analysis tools, we will investigate the role of the use of artificial intelligence in the field of advertising design, highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of this practice. Artificial intelligence has already been an integrated component of graphic design applications for several years and its contribution to making the design process considerably easier cannot be denied. However, we consider that the aesthetic sensibility of advertising products created exclusively by digital tools is questionable. We will argue that although advertising design products that are made by means of AI applications can be effective in terms of respecting graphic and aesthetic principles of composition, conveying a certain message or including specific symbols, their role as authentic outcomes of a creation process is problematic, as originality and aesthetic sensitivity are characteristics that can only be attributed to human designers. Following the analysis, we will reveal a series of implications and recommendations regarding the use of artificial intelligence in advertising design.

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Dana POPESCU-JOURDY (Université Lumière Lyon 2), Camelia CUȘNIR (Université de Bucarest), Marion FABRE (Université Lumière Lyon 2), Larrisa LUICĂ (Université de Bucarest), Anamaria NEAGU (Université de Bucarest), Simona NECULA (Université de Bucarest), Romina SURUGIU (Université de Bucarest), Elisabeth VERCHER (Université Lumière Lyon 2). *L'impact de l'intelligence artificielle (IA) sur les pratiques professionnelles dans l'enseignement universitaire de communication et médias*

L'intelligence artificielle suscite autant d'espoirs que de craintes. Les défis soulevés par l'émergence de l'IA sont bien présents dans l'éducation où on peut parler d'un moment disruptif au niveau des normes et des pratiques pédagogiques et d'apprentissage.

D'une part, l'IA est vue comme un outil qui devient de plus en plus important dans le processus d'enseignement, parfois améliorant tant l'expérience des enseignants, que des apprenants (Boissière & Bruillard, 2021). D'autre part, il y a des inquiétudes sur le fait que l'IA pourrait à un certain moment remplacer le rôle des enseignants, mais aussi par rapport aux implications éthiques soulevées par l'usage de cette technologie (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).

Ce panel d'experts discutera les résultats obtenus dans le cadre du projet de recherche « L'impact de l'intelligence artificielle (IA) sur les pratiques professionnelles dans l'enseignement universitaire de communication et médias » (IACOM), 2023-2024 qui a bénéficié du soutien financier de l'Agence universitaire de la Francophonie dans le cadre de l'« Appel à projets 2023 - Soutien aux Équipes de recherche en Europe Centrale et Orientale - SER-ECO ».

Les interventions visent à mieux comprendre l'impact de l'intelligence artificielle générative (IAG) dans l'enseignement supérieur, et notamment dans l'enseignement supérieur en information et en communication, mais aussi son impact dans les médias et dans le journalisme. Ainsi, on propose une compréhension approfondie de l'utilisation de l'IAG dans l'enseignement et l'apprentissage à travers des études de cas menées dans des différentes formations en France et en Roumanie. Aussi on s'intéresse à mieux comprendre les recommandations et de l'Observatoire UNESCO d'éthique de l'IA.

Interventions:

- Perception des étudiants sur l'usage d'IAG (Camelia Cușnir, Anamaria Neagu)
- Enseignants à la découverte de l'IA générative : défis et perspectives (Romina Surugiu, Elisabeth Vercher)
- L'utilisation de l'IA : inclusion et réussite universitaire (Marion Fabre)
- Perspectives interdisciplinaires : analyse des recommandations et de l'Observatoire UNESCO d'éthique de l'IA (Simona Necula, Larrisa Luică).

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Dana POPESCU-JOURDY (Université Lumière Lyon 2), Camelia CUȘNIR (University of Bucharest), Romina SURUGIU (University of Bucharest). *Students and teachers vs. AI. A comparative study France-Romania*

This research explores digital transformation within the educational sector, with a specific focus on how Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) is reshaping the educational landscape. The purpose of this case study is to assess the perceptions of students and educators within the field Media and Communication, focusing on potential benefits and risks associated with GenAI usage. A special attention was given to ethical considerations arising from utilizing these new tools in higher education. We used a survey performed on Media and Communication students and a focus group with faculty members specialized on Media, Communication and Digital Pedagogy at the University of Bucharest and Université Lumière 2 Lyon. We identified two different approaches to GenAI: enthusiasm among students and cautiousness among educators. Students have largely adopted GenAI tools in academic tasks while for educators the effective integration of AI into educational practices is still at the beginning. Both students and teachers are in favour of regulating the use of AI in universities.

Acknowledgements: The project "The impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on professional practices in university communication and media education" (IACOM) is supported by the Agence universitaire de la Francophonie under the 2023 Call for Projects - Support for Research Teams in Central and Eastern Europe - SER-ECO.

R

Andreea Roxana RĂCEANU (SNSPA) & Irina MARSH (SNSPA). *Public relations teaching and practice in the AI era*

The use of AI is pushing towards extensive changes in public relations, both in practice and its supporting academic training. Our paper is focused on the dimensions of strategic public relations between the academia and industry professionals. The aim of the proposed study is to discuss the potential of

university-industry relations (UIR) in the area of public relations, for fostering developments meant to meet present and future challenges and opportunities brought about by recent and expected developments in technology.

There are areas where the AI integration within the PR domain already has a major impact: content creation optimization, personalised communication enhancement, AI powered analytics, proactive crisis management. However, as AI becomes more prevalent, ethical practice and ensuring transparency, fairness and privacy are crucial for maintaining the credibility and reputation of the profession. In this context, university is best placed to ensure that the challenges are addressed and innovative solutions are researched and adopted.

Starting from the classic two-way symmetrical model of public relations based on a partnership between two interpreters, the paper discusses the relational dimensions between the university and its important publics, among which, highlighted as most important, there are the students, teachers, and relevant employers in the field. The authors present the results of the quantitative research they carried out so far on the topic, based on in depth interviews, by which they investigated the expectations that these publics have from each other. The practical implications aimed to identify areas for partnership. The main contribution of the paper is the problematization of the future directions of relations between the universities that offer academic training in the field of public relations and their relevant audiences, in the context of AI development. A set of research dimensions and specific actionable areas are proposed regarding teaching methodology, content and strategic partnerships.

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S

Carmen-Daniela SULTĂNESCU (SNSPA). Manipularea dezbatelor publice prin utilizarea unor conturi false în social media

Acest articol și-a propus să analizeze modul în care a evoluat comportamentul neautentic coordonat (CIB) în intervalul 2023 - 2024 pentru a oferi o imagine mai cuprinzătoare asupra evoluției și trendurilor privind manipularea dezbatelor publice prin utilizarea unor conturi false în social media, inclusiv prin utilizarea inteligenței artificiale.

Deși există studii care au analizat comportamentul neautentic coordonat (Maza, Cola, & Tesconi, 2022; Murero, 2023; de-Lima-Santos & Ceron, 2024), nu au fost efectuate cercetări care să analizeze cum a evoluat această amenințare pe internet prin prisma utilizării inteligenței artificiale.

Printr-o cercetare care a utilizat analiza calitativă și cantitativă aplicată la un corpus de 22 de rețele cu comportament neautentic coordonat (CIB), identificate și neutralizate de către META, am încercat să răspund la următoarele întrebări de cercetare: 1) care au fost principalele țări care au coordonat astfel de rețele și spațiile/ audiențele vizate, 2) care au fost principalele platforme pe care au fost create și dezvoltate aceste rețele, pentru a cerceta dacă rețelele au fost cantonate la nivelul unor platforme sau au fost disperate - cross-platforms, în încercarea de a acapara audiență, 3) care au fost rețelele care utilizau cel mai mare număr de conturi fictive, respectiv cu cel mai mare număr de urmăritori, 4) dacă modul de acțiune a implicat utilizarea inteligenței artificiale.

Datele au arătat că cea mai utilizată tactică bazată pe GenAI a fost folosirea unor fotografii de profil generate de Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN), în încercarea de a conferi credibilitate și unicitate conturilor.

Acest studiu este limitat de faptul că rapoartele trimestriale ale META din intervalul analizat nu reflectă totalitatea măsurilor de securitate, ci arată investigațiile cele mai relevante pentru a ajuta la înțelegerea amenințărilor și a evoluției acestora.

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Romina SURUGIU (Universite de Bucarest), Elisabeth VERCHER (Université Lumière Lyon 2). Enseignants à la découverte de l'IA générative : défis et perspectives

L'intelligence artificielle générative (IAG) oblige l'enseignement supérieur à repenser les pratiques traditionnelles d'enseignement ainsi que les curricula. Notre but est de déterminer la perception des étudiants et des enseignants en Sciences de l'Information et de la Communication (notre étude de cas) sur les avantages et les menaces potentielles de l'utilisation de l'IAG et, notamment, sur les implications éthiques qui émergent de cette situation. Notre contribution empirique à la compréhension de ce terrain nous fournira également des ressources afin de formuler des pistes de préconisations en vue de l'utilisation de l'IAG dans l'enseignement supérieur. L'approche comparative entre nos deux terrains d'observation (français et roumain) nous permettra de comprendre les différences entre les deux contextes académiques.

Remerciements. Le projet de recherche «L'impact de l'intelligence artificielle (IA) sur les pratiques professionnelles dans l'enseignement universitaire de communication et médias» (IACOM) bénéficie du soutien financier de l'Agence universitaire de la Francophonie dans le cadre de l'«Appel à projets 2023 - Soutien aux Équipes de recherche en Europe Centrale et Orientale - SER-ECO».

Adriana ȘTEFĂNEL, Antonio AMUZA (Universitatea din București). *Tentația autoritarismului în rândul tinerilor din România: O analiză de date secundare*

Prezentarea explorează tendințele autoritariste ale tinerilor români în contextul anului electoral 2024. Pentru a investiga atracția autoritarismului în rândul tinerilor români vom utiliza date secundare din World Value Survey și sondajul IRES „Tinerii din România în anul electoral 2024”. Vom analiza preferințele politice și atitudinile sociale ale acestei generații, evidențiind măsura în care această atracție există precum și factorii care contribuie la o înclinație către regimuri autoritare. Cercetarea noastră va examina variabile precum nivelul de educație, sex, mediul de rezidență, valori și influența mediului social, oferind o imagine detaliată a motivelor din spatele acestei tendințe. Ne propunem să oferim înțelegere aprofundată a fenomenului și să deschidem o dezbatere privind soluțiile pentru consolidarea valorilor democratice în rândul tinerilor.

Rodica Melinda ȘUȚU (University of Bucharest). *The moral compass of journalists: Navigating moral dilemmas*

This research focuses on the comprehensive findings of the World Journalism Study 2023 project (<https://worldsofjournalism.org/>) in order to explore the evolving landscape of journalism in the digital age from the point of view of journalistic ethics. The study was carried out in Romania between October 2022 and September 2023 through an online questionnaire with 367 respondents. Drawing from the results obtained through quantitative methods, this research aims to provide a nuanced qualitative analysis that highlights the ethical dilemmas of the Romanian journalists facing both domestic and global challenges. The findings show that most of the journalists interviewed for the World Journalism Study 2023 project in Romania consider that ethical orientation should always be determined by professional standards regardless of situation and personal judgment. They use professional codes of ethics in order to provide protection against external pressure or internal bias. A majority of the respondents strongly reject controversial reporting methods such as paying for confidential information, accepting money and products from sources or broadcasting stories not yet verified. The beliefs expressed by the majority of the Romanian journalists interviewed for this study align with the core ethical principles highlighted by relevant scholars and professionals (Craig, 2015; Duncan, 2023; Zion, 2015; Keeble, 2009; Harcup, 2007). In that respect, truth and accuracy are the essential values that journalists should adhere to if they are to report responsibly, followed by verification of information, independence and allegiances (White, 2015; Ward, 2019).

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T

Santiago TEJEDOR (Autonomous University of Barcelona), Cristina PULIDO (Autonomous University of Barcelona), Laura CERVI (Autonomous University of Barcelona), & Stephanie VICK (Autonomous University of Barcelona). *How are communication companies adopting AI?*

This study investigates the adoption and application of artificial intelligence (AI) in communication companies, aiming to map out the current landscape and provide an in-depth understanding of how AI technologies are integrated into journalistic practices. The primary research question addresses how communication companies are adopting AI. Using a descriptive, explanatory, and exploratory methodology, the study employs a case study approach as suggested by Yin (1989). This approach is particularly suitable for emerging topics, allowing researchers to analyze phenomena in real-world contexts. The methodology includes research tools such as questionnaires and bibliographic analysis, ensuring a comprehensive contextualization of the subject matter. The study leverages key bibliographic sources, including a report by the Observatory for the Innovation of News of the Digital Society (OI2) and "Artificial Intelligence in Journalism" by Tejedor-Calvo (2023), which conduct international mappings of media using automation. Results indicate that 108 media outlets have adopted AI, with newspapers leading the way (72), followed by television (14), news agencies (14), radio (5), and multiplatform media (3). Geographically, the US is at the forefront with 22 outlets, followed by Spain (14) and the UK (9). Text generation emerges as the primary use of AI, with 46 companies utilizing this technology. Notably, 27 companies have developed proprietary AI solutions. Surveys with experts highlight fact-checking as the most important AI application despite the predominance of text generation tools. The study underscores

the uneven pace of AI adoption across different media types and regions, revealing a greater inclination towards AI in digital newspapers. It also showcases the versatility of AI tools, which are employed for various functions within media operations. This comprehensive overview emphasizes the significant trend towards AI adoption, driven by its potential to streamline processes and enhance journalistic practices.

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V

Natalia VASILENDIUC (University of Bucharest), Alexandra BARDAN (University of Bucharest), Andrada FISCUTEAN (University of Bucharest), Antonia MATEI (University of Bucharest), Carmen IONESCU (University of Bucharest), Rodica Melinda ȘUȚU (University of Bucharest), Bogdan OPREA (University of Bucharest), Gheorghe ANGHEL (University of Bucharest), *Navigating the Evolving Landscape of Journalism in the Digital Age: Insights from the World Journalism Study 2023 on the Romanian Media Landscape*

This panel leverages the comprehensive findings of the World Journalism Study 2023 (WJS3) project (<https://worldsofjournalism.org/>) to explore the evolving landscape of journalism in the digital age. Our aim is to provide a nuanced analysis that combines global insights from WJS3 with a specific focus on the Romanian media scene, exploring both the challenges and opportunities journalists face today.

The media industry is undergoing a profound transformation due to digital disruption and shifting information consumption patterns (Allan et al., 2019; Franklin, 2016; Picard, 2010). Journalists are at the forefront of this change, constantly adapting their roles and practices to navigate a complex and fast paced environment (Deuze, 2007). Drawing on the global research of the WJS3 project, this panel examines these changes from several critical angles and provides a detailed and contextualized exploration of how these dynamics are playing out in Romania.

The WJS3 project offers valuable insight on the level of editorial control journalists have over their content in different countries. This panel examines how ownership structures, whether private or state-controlled, influence editorial autonomy. We will discuss the impact of political pressure and economic constraints on the ability of journalists to report freely, providing comparative insights between different Romanian media outlets.

As the media is increasingly relying on technology, the roles of journalists are constantly evolving (Chadwick, 2013). This panel will explore whether journalists are primarily storytellers or whether they are increasingly taking on the role of analysts, fact-checkers, and data journalists. By analyzing WJS3 data, we will highlight the skills required to succeed in modern journalism and show how these roles are changing in different regions, with a particular focus on Romania.

Technology and cultural context significantly shape journalistic practices (Hollifield and Coffey, 2023). This panel will discuss the rise of social media and citizen journalism and their impact on traditional media worldwide. We will explore how cultural differences influence journalistic approaches to sensitive issues and investigative reporting. Using WJS3 findings and examples from the Romanian media landscape, we will provide insights into these critical issues.

Journalists are exposed to numerous risks, including threats of violence, intimidation, and censorship (UNESCO, 2017). This panel will analyze how these security threats manifest in different countries, particularly in Romania. We will examine the vulnerable position investigative journalists find themselves and the prevalence of state censorship, using the WJS3 data to understand the broader implications for press freedom and the safety of journalists.

Utilizing the WJS3 framework, we will conduct an in-depth analysis of the Romanian media landscape, highlighting the risks and opportunities faced by journalists in this region. Romania, with its unique political and economic history, provides a compelling case study for examining the broader trends affecting journalism worldwide. The panel will take an in-depth look at various media outlets in Romania, from established national dailies to emerging online startups, and how they are navigating the challenges of digital transformation. For example, we will explore how the WJS3 data on security threats manifests itself in the Romanian context. Are investigative journalists particularly vulnerable to intimidation or violence? We will also examine the state of press freedom in Romania and the extent to which state censorship has prevailed.

The panel will also look at the impact of digital technologies on the media industry, audience behavior, and the spread of misinformation. We will discuss strategies for journalists to adapt to and thrive in this new environment, including the rise of mobile journalism and its impact on news gathering techniques. Are journalists in Romania equipped with the necessary skills and resources to use these new tools effectively?

Social media presents both opportunities and challenges for journalists. While it can improve audience engagement and content distribution, it is also a breeding ground for misinformation (Wardle, 2017). The panel will discuss strategies for journalists in Romania to combat “fake news” and ensure the credibility of their work.

Presentations and panelists:

- An overview of the Worlds of Journalism Study 3 and methodological aspects (Natalia Vasilendiuc)
- Behind the headline: How journalists see themselves (Alexandra Bardan)

- The pressure to inform - internal factors. The workday realities of journalists (Andrada Fiscutean)
- From watchdog to guide: How journalists see themselves in society (Antonia Matei)
- Professional experience in journalism and perceived importance of journalistic roles (Carmen Ionescu)
- The moral compass of journalists: Navigating ethical dilemmas (Rodica Melinda Şuţu)
- Safety and media: Reporting during the covid pandemic, amidst hate speech, public discrediting, and surveillance (Bogdan Oprea)
- Safety, support, and protection: Unveiling the challenges faced by journalists in modern media (Gheorghe Anghel)

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